

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

2
0
2
4

No 11

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

*Elektron nashr. 219 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 7-noyabrda ruxsat etildi.*

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:
Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, t.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, i.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy Majlisi qonunchilik palatasi deputati
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, i.f.n., professor, MIM akademiyasi rektori
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Ilmiy ishlar va innovatsiyalar bo'yicha prorektori
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, i.f.d., prof., Navoiy davlat pedagogika instituti rektori
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, p.f.f.d., (PhD), Buxoro muhandislik-texnologiya instituti rektori
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Hududiy ta'lim muassasalari va markazlar bo'yicha prorektor v.b.
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, i.f.d., TDIUprofessor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, i.f.n., TDIU professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, t.f.d., Rossiya xalqlar do'stligi universiteti professori
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, i.f.d., prof., Xalqaro "Nordik" universiteti rektori
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, i.f.d., TSUE professori
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farxod, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, f.f.d. profesor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, SamDu IS instituti professori
Cham Tat Huei, (PhD) USCI universiteti professori, Malayziya
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, i.f.d., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri o'rinbosari
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, i.f.f.d.,(PhD) "El-yurt umidi" jamg'armasi ijrochi direktori o'rinbosari
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, t.f.f.d.,(PhD) TAQU katta o'qituvchisi
Djudi Smetana, p.f.n., Pitsburg davlat universiteti dosenti, Pittsburgh, Kansas, AQSH
Krissi Lyuis, p.f.n., Pitsburg davlat universiteti dosenti, Pittsburgh, Kansas, AQSH
Ali Kopak (Али Кўнак), i.f.d., prof., Karabuk universiteti dosenti, Turkiya
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, i.f.n., "LUKOIL-Energoservis" Kompaniyasi iqtisodchisi, Moskva.
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, i.f.f.d., (PhD) TDIU dotsenti
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, Turkiya Anqara universiteti doktoranti
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Oqil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjaevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, DSc, Prof., Minister of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Rae Kwon Chung, honorary professor of TSUE, Nobel laureate, South Korea,

Osman Mesten, member of the Turkish Parliament, head of the Turkey-Uzbekistan Friendship Society

Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, DSc, Prof., Deputy of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich CSc, Prof., Rector of Academy of Labor and Social Relations

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, DSc, Prof., TSUE Vice-Rector for Scientific Affairs and Innovation

Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhritdinovich, DSc, Prof., Rector of the Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Siddikova Sadokat Ghaforovna, PhD, Rector of the Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, DSc, Prof., acting Vice-rector for regional educational institutions and centers of TSUE

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, CSc, Prof., of TSUE

Slizovsky Dimitriy Yegorovich, DSc, Prof., of the People's Friendship University of Russia

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, DSc, Prof., Rector of International "Nordic" University

Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja ugli, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of the DGPO of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the DCECGPO of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Eshtayev Alisher Abduganievich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, PhD in Philology, Professor.

Shoira Azimovna Musaeva, professor of SamDu IS Institute

Cham Tat Huei, PhD, professor at USCI University, Malaysia

Buzrukhanov Sarvarkhan Munavvarkhanovich, DSc, Deputy Minister of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, PhD, deputy of executive director of the "El-yurt umidi" fund

Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, PhD, Senior Lecturer at Tashkent University of Architecture and Construction

Judy Smetana CSc, Associate Professor, Pittsburgh State University, Pittsburgh, Kansas, USA

Chrissy Lewis CSc, Associate Professor, Pittsburgh State University, Pittsburgh, Kansas, USA

Ali Konak DSc, Prof., Associate Professor of Karabuk University, Turkey

Glazova Marina Viktorovna, CSc, economist at LUKOIL-Energoservis Company, Moscow.

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, associate professor of TSUE

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, doctoral student at Ankara University, Turkey

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, independent researcher of TSUE

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, t.f.d., profesor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, f.f.d., TDIU professori
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, i. f. n., TDAU dotsenti
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, f.f.n., Farg'ona davlat universiteti dotsenti
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, i.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, p.f.f.d., (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, i.f.f.d. (PhD), Alfraganus universiteti dotsenti
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, i.f.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, i.f.d., TMI dotsenti
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti,
O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi
huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali
O‘zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta’lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi
huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori
bilan ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Iqtisodiyotning pul mablag'lari bilan ta'minlanganlik darajasini oshirish yo'llari.....	16
Sindarov Sherzod Egamberdiyevich, Yusupov Muxammadali Soxib o'g'li	
Driving economic growth through service exports.....	20
Rahimov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida jamoat tashkilotlarini boshqarishni takomillashtirishda jahon tajribasi.....	27
Raxmonov Abduxalil Rasulovich	
Raqamli marketing va mijozlar bilan ishlashning yangi usullari.....	31
Ummatov Avaz Muydinovich	
Soliq tushumlarini shakllantirish ko'rsatkichlari asosida soliq salohiyatini baholash usullari	35
Jo'raev Husan	
Bevosita soliqqa tortish darajasini ko'paytirish omillari.....	41
Qodirov Baxodir Qudratovich	
Tijorat banklarining xo'jalik subyektlari bilan amalga oshiriladigan muddatli valyuta operatsiyalarini rivojlantirish	47
Ibodullaeva Ma'rifat To'lqin qizi	
Tovarlarning monopol yuqori (past) narxlarini aniqlashni takomillashtirish masalalari	52
Mingboev Asqar Qandaharovich	
Bojxona faoliyatini transformatsiyalashda innovatsion boshqaruvni takomillashtirishga oid xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	59
Ro'ziboyev Muhiddin Xushnudovich	
Harnessing foreign direct investment for sustainable economic growth in Central Asia: policy challenges and opportunities.....	63
Mukhammedova Azizakhon Ikromjon kizi	
Mintaqa innovatsion faoliyatida tavakkalchilikni boshqarishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	68
Sapayeva N.K.	
Examining Uzbekistan's foreign trade indicators	72
Berdivaliyeva Madina Komiljon qizi	
Yo'l bo'yidagi xizmat ko'rsatish infratuzilmasini baholash: xizmat sifati va transport xavfsizligini oshirish.....	78
Egamberduyev Odil Buriboyevich	
Роль инноваций в гибком управлении проектами.....	82
Касимова Наима Жахангировна	
Sug'urta bozorini tartibga solishni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	87
Tursunova Maftuna Agzamovna	
Mintaqada turizm sohasini rivojlantirishda madaniy turizm resurslarining o'rni va roli	91
Ro'zmetov Baxodir Shomurotovich	
Sug'urta kompaniyalarining kapital bozoridagi emission faolligini oshirishning iqtisodiy asoslari	97
Shodmonova Munisa Nizamjon qizi	
Korxonaning tashqi bozorga chiqishida marketing strategiyasining samaradorligini baholash.....	104
Akramov Bo'ribek Faxriddin o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida korxonalar innovatsion faoliyatini boshqarish	110
Saipova Dilnoza Shuxratovna	

Xalqaro standartlar asosida kapital qo'yilmalar hisobini takomillashtirish.....	114
Egamberdieva Salima Rayimovna, Bozorov Yashnarbek Xayrulla o'g'li	
Investitsiyalar samaradorligini baholash va ularga ta'sir etuvchi omillar tahlili.....	120
Jo'raev Paxlavonjon Usarovich	
Soliq qarzdorliklarini yuzaga kelishining ilmiy nazariy asoslari tadqiqi	127
Ostonaqulov Alisher Abdurashidovich	
Korxonalarni moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash va ularga imtiyozlar berishni takomillashtirish masalalari.....	132
Z.T. Mirzayev	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida korxonalarda raqamli marketingning ahamiyati.....	139
M.Vohobjonova	
Положение электронной коммерции на международном и национальном уровнях	142
Абдуганиев Учкун Хабибулла угли, Орифбоев Озод Азатович	
Korporativ resurslardan samarali foydalanish orqali kichik biznes subyektlarini barqaror rivojlantirish va samaradorligini oshirish.....	148
Jalolova Muazzamxon Akbarjonovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligida kartoshka ishlab chiqarish funksiyasi.....	151
Avazmurodov Islom Nusratullo o'g'li, Muratov Shukurullo Abduraimovich	
Tovar-moddiy resurslar harakati bo'yicha logistik muammolar va ularni bartaraf etishning samarali yechimlari	155
Sherzod Xolmurodovich Pardayev	
Ta'lim va ilm-fan sohasida inson kapitali konsepsiyasining amalga oshish bosqichlari yo'nalishlari.....	159
Nasretdinova Aziza Adxamjonovna , Bozarov Elyor Boboqulovich	
Влияние цифровой валюты центральных банков (CBDC) на международную торговлю и финансовые отношения: Анализ и перспективы	164
Номозали Хайдаров	
Raqamli transformatsiya va tadbirkorlik: kichik biznes uchun yangi imkoniyatlar va chora-tadbirlar	167
Sobirjonov Sanjar Sobirjonovich, TDIU magistranti	
O'zbekiston respublikasida aholini samarali ish bilan ta'minlash istiqbollari.....	172
Raxmatullayeva Shahnoza Xamidovna, Sadriddinova Sevinchxon Sadriddin qizi	
Aylanma mablag'lar aylanuvchanligini tezlashtirishning asosiy yo'llari	179
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich	
Mintaqada to'qimachilik sanoatining iqtisodiy holati tahlili (Xorazm viloyati misolida)	185
Xudoyorova M.O	
Мировой опыт стратегического управления финансовыми ресурсами акционерных обществ.....	190
Абдалиев Айдос Бахтиярович	
Sug'urta faoliyatida axborot jarayonlarini vtomatlashtirishning nazariy asoslari.....	196
Shakirov O'tkirbek Taxirovich	
Yerlardan maqsadli foydalanishni aniqlash uslubi.....	199
Yunusov Begench Mavlanberdievich	
Iqtisodiyotda real sektorning ahamiyati va uning rivojlanishi.....	204
Amirqulov Umarali Akram o'g'li	
Yashil iqtisodiyotni baholash amaliyoti va indikatorlari	208
Feruz Raxmatova Yusupjanovna	
O'zbekistonda korxonalarni boshqarishda raqamli texnologiyalardan qo'llash yo'nalishlari	213
Qo'chqorov Tohir Safarovich, To'ychiyev Akmaljon Abdulatif o'g'li	

HARNESSING FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT FOR SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH IN CENTRAL ASIA: POLICY CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

ORCID: 0009-0001-6786-9507

Mukhammedova Azizakhon Ikromjon kizi

PhD Candidate in Econometrics and Statistics
Westminster International University in Tashkent

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot Markaziy Osiyo davlatlarida, xususan, Qozog'iston, O'zbekiston va Turkmanistonda to'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarning (FDI) iqtisodiy o'sish va barqaror rivojlanishga ta'sirini o'rganadi. Zamonaviy empirik adabiyotlar tahliliga asoslanib, tadqiqot to'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarning kapital shakllanishi, texnologiyalar transferi va bandlikni oshirishdagi foydali ta'sirini ta'kidlaydi. Tadqiqot, shuningdek, mintaqada to'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalar oqimini cheklovchi to'siqlarni, jumladan, siyosiy beqarorlik, infratuzilma yetishmovchiligi va qazib olish sanoatiga qaramlikni tahlil qiladi. Ushbu maqola yashil to'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarni rivojlantirishni tavsiya etadi va ularning uzoq muddatli barqaror rivojlanishni qo'llab-quvvatlash va atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilishdagi ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi. Asosiy siyosiy tavsiyalar boshqaruv tizimlarini takomillashtirish, moliyaviy bozorlarni yaxshilash, turli sohalarda to'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarni diversifikatsiya qilish va yashil investitsiyalarni rag'batlantirish uchun soliq islohotlarini amalga oshirishni o'z ichiga oladi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ushbu muammolarni hal qilish orqali Markaziy Osiyo davlatlari to'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarni barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanish mexanizmi sifatida samaraliroq foydalanishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: To'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalar (FDI), iqtisodiy o'sish, barqaror rivojlanish, Markaziy Osiyo, yashil investitsiyalar, siyosiy islohotlar, qayta tiklanadigan energiya.

Abstract: This study examines the influence of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) on economic growth and sustainable development within Central Asian nations, particularly emphasizing Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Turkmenistan. Based on an examination of contemporary empirical literature, the study underscores the beneficial impacts of foreign direct investment on capital formation, technology transfer, and employment generation. The research further delineates the obstacles that constrain foreign direct investment inflows within the region, which encompass political instability, deficiencies in infrastructure, and a dependence on extractive industries. This paper advocates for the advancement of Green Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), highlighting its significance in fostering long-term sustainable development and safeguarding environmental integrity. The principal policy recommendations encompass the enhancement of governance frameworks, the improvement of financial markets, the diversification of foreign direct investment across various sectors, and the implementation of tax reforms designed to incentivize green investments. The results indicate that by tackling these challenges, Central Asian nations can more effectively utilize foreign direct investment as a mechanism for sustainable economic development.

Key words: Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Economic Growth, Sustainable Development, Central Asia, Green FDI, Policy Reforms, Renewable Energy.

Аннотация: В данном исследовании рассматривается влияние прямых иностранных инвестиций (FDI) на экономический рост и устойчивое развитие в странах Центральной Азии, с особым акцентом на Казахстан, Узбекистан и Туркменистан. На основе анализа современной эмпирической литературы исследование подчеркивает положительное воздействие прямых иностранных инвестиций на формирование капитала, передачу технологий и создание рабочих мест. В работе также описываются препятствия, ограничивающие приток прямых иностранных инвестиций в регионе, включая политическую нестабильность, недостатки инфраструктуры и зависимость от добывающих отраслей. Статья выступает за развитие "зеленых" прямых иностранных инвестиций, подчеркивая их важность в содействии долгосрочному устойчивому развитию и защите окружающей среды. Основные рекомендации включают улучшение управленческих структур, совершенствование финансовых рынков, диверсификацию прямых иностранных инвестиций в различные сектора и проведение налоговых реформ, направленных на стимулирование зеленых инвестиций. Результаты показывают, что, решая эти проблемы, страны Центральной Азии могут более эффективно использовать прямые иностранные инвестиции как механизм устойчивого экономического развития.

Ключевые слова: Прямые иностранные инвестиции (FDI), экономический рост, устойчивое развитие, Центральная Азия, зеленые инвестиции, реформы политики, возобновляемая энергия.

INTRODUCTION

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is extensively acknowledged as a vital catalyst for economic growth and development, particularly within developing and emerging markets. FDI presents an opportunity for nations in Central Asia to address capital deficiencies, facilitate the transfer of technology, and enhance employment prospects. In recent decades, countries in Central Asia most notably Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Turkmenistan have made considerable progress in attracting foreign investments, especially in the domains of natural resources and infrastructure.

Nevertheless, these nations encounter numerous obstacles in their efforts to attract sustainable and diversified foreign direct investment flows, such as political instability, insufficient infrastructure, and reliance on extractive industries [6, 5]. The increasing significance of Green Foreign Direct Investment, which emphasizes environmentally sustainable and responsible investments, provides Central Asian nations with a viable avenue for achieving enduring sustainable development. Investments in renewable energy, green infrastructure, and technological innovation are regarded as essential strategies for mitigating carbon emissions and conforming to international environmental standards [7, 4].

This study investigates the influence of foreign direct investment (FDI) on economic growth and sustainable development in Central Asia, emphasizing the policy ramifications associated with the promotion of diversified and environmentally sustainable FDI.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is instrumental in promoting economic growth, especially within developing and emerging economies. FDI is frequently regarded as a mechanism to address deficiencies in capital, facilitate the transfer of technology, and generate employment opportunities. Furthermore, it fosters managerial proficiency and incorporates developing nations into the global economy, thereby augmenting their productivity and competitiveness [6].

FDI is typically classified into two primary categories: Greenfield investments and mergers and acquisitions (M&A). Greenfield investments pertain to the creation of new facilities, whereas mergers and acquisitions involve the procurement of existing enterprises [1]. These investments have a direct influence on the economic growth of host countries, as they introduce foreign capital and technology, improve production capabilities, and promote international trade [5].

Theoretical Frameworks Concerning Foreign Direct Investment and Economic Development

Several theoretical models have been formulated to elucidate the relationship between foreign direct investment and economic growth. The endogenous growth theory suggests that FDI plays a significant role in promoting long-term economic growth through the facilitation of knowledge spillovers, advancements in technology, and the development of human capital [6]. FDI is regarded as a source of external financing that alleviates investment deficiencies in underdeveloped capital markets, as exemplified by numerous developing nations (Villaverde, 2015).

Conversely, the Solow-Swan growth model posits that FDI contributes to economic growth solely in a temporary manner, as the phenomenon of diminishing returns becomes evident [3]. Nevertheless, empirical evidence frequently substantiates the perspective that FDI exerts a beneficial and enduring influence on economic growth, especially when complemented by robust institutional frameworks and macroeconomic stability [5].

Empirical Evidence Regarding the Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Economic Growth

An expanding corpus of empirical research underscores the beneficial impacts of FDI on economic growth. Doytch [4] identified that FDI in the services and technology sectors plays a significant role in economic development through job creation and productivity enhancement. In a similar vein, a scholar underscored the significance of FDI in developing nations, particularly in fostering infrastructure development and facilitating technological innovation [2].

Within the framework of Sub-Saharan Africa, Ugwu and Okoye [6] conducted an examination of the impact of FDI on the economic growth of nations including Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa. The authors concluded that FDI had a positive impact on the gross domestic product (GDP) of Nigeria and Ghana; however, its effect on the economy of South Africa was found to be negative. This discrepancy indicates that the influence of FDI on economic growth may differ based on the institutional framework and macroeconomic conditions of the host country.

Moreover, FDI is instrumental in the advancement of infrastructure within host nations. For example, a study conducted by [5] demonstrated that FDI exerted a significant positive influence on infrastructure development in Southeast Asia, with China identified as a principal recipient of infrastructure-focused FDI. This category of

investment is crucial for the development of transportation, energy, and communication infrastructures, which subsequently facilitate additional economic expansion.

The Significance of Corporate Taxation in Foreign Direct Investment

Corporate taxation constitutes a significant determinant affecting the inflow of FDI. Reduced corporate tax rates are associated with an increase in FDI, as international investors aim to optimize their returns [1]. A research investigation conducted by Dreger and Zhang [3] examined the correlation between corporate taxation and FDI inflows within the European Union, emphasizing that nations with more advantageous tax policies demonstrated greater efficacy in attracting FDI. Tax reforms designed to simplify tax structures and alleviate tax burdens have the potential to enhance a nation's competitiveness and appeal as a destination for foreign investment (Villaverde, 2015). Furthermore, nations that have adopted International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) have observed a rise in FDI inflows, as the standardization of financial reporting enhances transparency and bolsters investor confidence [6].

Foreign Direct Investment and Sustainable Development

FDI serves not only as a catalyst for economic growth but also as a significant contributor to the advancement of sustainable development. Investments in green technologies, renewable energy, and environmentally sustainable industries have emerged as a priority for numerous nations [6]. Countries including Slovenia and Germany have reaped advantages from Green FDI, which has played a significant role in the advancement of sustainable infrastructure, the safeguarding of the environment, and the mitigation of carbon emissions (Villaverde, 2015).

The research conducted by Doytch [4] emphasizes that FDI in renewable energy sectors possesses the capacity to diminish a nation's dependence on non-renewable resources while fostering sustainable economic growth. Countries implementing policies that encourage Green FDI are positioned to attract investors who prioritize environmental sustainability, thereby promoting long-term development that aligns with global sustainability objectives.

Challenges in Attracting Foreign Direct Investment

Notwithstanding the advantages associated with FDI, various challenges impede the capacity of developing nations to attract and retain such investments. Political instability, corruption, insufficient infrastructure, and restrictive regulatory frameworks constitute significant challenges encountered by numerous host nations [6]. The aforementioned challenges engender uncertainty and amplify the risks inherent in foreign investments.

Furthermore, research indicates that nations with underdeveloped financial markets encounter difficulties in attracting FDI, as investors tend to favor environments that facilitate easy access to credit and capital [1]. It is imperative for governments to prioritize the implementation of reforms that enhance the efficacy of financial institutions and foster a stable macroeconomic environment, thereby increasing their appeal to foreign investors.

FDI constitutes an essential element in fostering economic growth and promoting sustainable development within developing nations. It facilitates the influx of foreign capital, technology, and expertise, thereby addressing deficiencies in domestic investment and fostering sustainable economic growth over the long term. FDI has demonstrated positive impacts on infrastructure development, productivity, and employment; however, the magnitude of these advantages is contingent upon the institutional framework, regulatory environment, and macroeconomic stability of the host country. Countries that undertake tax reforms, encourage Green FDI, and enhance their financial markets are likely to attract a greater volume of foreign investments, consequently promoting sustainable economic growth. Nevertheless, it is imperative that challenges such as political instability and insufficient infrastructure are addressed in order to fully leverage the advantages of FDI.

RESULTS

The literature review elucidates several significant findings pertaining to the role of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in promoting economic growth and sustainable development within Central Asian nations. These findings indicate that FDI exerts a considerable influence on economic growth; however, its efficacy is substantially contingent upon various factors, including the institutional environment of the host country, tax policies, and the commitment to sustainable development.

The Positive Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Economic Growth: Evidence indicates that FDI has a beneficial effect on economic growth in Central Asian nations through the enhancement of capital inflows, the transfer of technology, and the generation of employment opportunities [6, 4]. This assertion is particularly applicable in sectors such as infrastructure development and manufacturing, wherein FDI has been instrumental in enhancing productivity and efficiency [5]. Nevertheless, the extent of impact differs among nations, contingent upon their institutional frameworks and regulatory environments.

Sectoral Distribution of Foreign Direct Investment: FDI has exhibited an uneven distribution across various sectors. In numerous instances, investments have been predominantly directed toward the extractive

industries, especially in the oil and gas sectors, as evidenced by the cases of Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan [3]. Although these investments have contributed to substantial GDP growth, they have concurrently resulted in an economic reliance on natural resources. In contrast, Uzbekistan has initiated efforts to diversify its FDI inflows, successfully attracting investments in sectors such as renewable energy, manufacturing, and infrastructure. This strategic approach contributes to a more balanced and sustainable growth trajectory [2].

The Role of Corporate Taxation and Financial Reforms: The existing literature identifies corporate taxation as a significant factor influencing FDI inflows. Countries characterized by advantageous tax regimes are likely to draw increased levels of FDI, as investors endeavor to optimize their returns [1]. Furthermore, financial reforms, including the implementation of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), have enhanced transparency and bolstered investor confidence, resulting in heightened FDI inflows in Sub-Saharan Africa. This trend presents the potential for replication in Central Asia [6].

Green Foreign Direct Investment and Sustainable Development: Central Asian nations, notably Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan, are increasingly attracting Green Foreign Direct Investment, which emphasizes renewable energy and environmentally sustainable infrastructure (Villaverde, 2015). These investments not only stimulate economic growth but also enhance environmental sustainability through the reduction of carbon emissions and the promotion of energy efficiency. Green FDI is regarded as an essential element of enduring sustainable development, positioning Central Asian nations in accordance with international initiatives aimed at addressing climate change [4].

Challenges in Attracting Foreign Direct Investment: Notwithstanding the prospective advantages of FDI, Central Asian nations encounter numerous obstacles in their efforts to attract and maintain foreign investments. Political instability, corruption, and insufficient infrastructure represent substantial obstacles that elevate the risks associated with FDI [6]. Moreover, the landlocked geographical characteristics of many Central Asian nations contribute to elevated transportation expenses, thereby diminishing their appeal to investors focused on export-oriented opportunities [3]. Addressing these challenges is essential for enhancing FDI inflows and realizing their full potential.

Policy Implications and Recommendations

Drawing upon the findings from the literature, a number of policy implications and recommendations can be articulated to optimize the advantages of foreign direct investment in Central Asian nations:

Enhancement of Institutional Frameworks: Central Asian countries must enhance their institutional frameworks and implement regulatory reforms to establish a stable and transparent business environment that fosters foreign investments. This includes improving governance, reducing bureaucratic inefficiencies, and implementing robust anti-corruption measures. A transparent regulatory environment is essential for fostering investor confidence and attracting long-term foreign direct investment [6].

Promoting Sectoral Diversification of Foreign Direct Investment: To mitigate dependence on natural resources, Central Asian countries should pursue diversification of foreign direct investment across various sectors. While investments in extractive industries have contributed to economic growth, excessive reliance on these sectors can lead to vulnerabilities from commodity price fluctuations. Promoting investments in renewable energy, manufacturing, and technology can foster more sustainable and inclusive growth [5, 4].

Tax Incentives and Financial Reforms: Governments in Central Asia should consider providing competitive tax incentives aimed at attracting foreign investors. Reforms in corporate taxation, combined with the implementation of global financial standards such as IFRS, can enhance transparency, alleviate tax burdens, and create a more conducive investment environment [1]. Evidence suggests that such reforms can significantly boost foreign direct investment inflows and may be effectively implemented in Central Asia.

Promotion of Green Foreign Direct Investment: Policymakers in Central Asia should actively promote Green Foreign Direct Investment by formulating policies that incentivize investments in renewable energy and sustainable infrastructure. This may include offering subsidies or tax credits for environmentally sustainable investments, simplifying regulations related to renewable energy projects, and ensuring that infrastructure development aligns with environmental sustainability goals (Villaverde, 2015). Attracting Green FDI will stimulate economic growth and help Central Asian nations achieve their environmental and climate objectives.

Enhancing Infrastructure and Mitigating Trade Expenses: Governments must prioritize infrastructure development to alleviate transportation costs associated with being landlocked. This includes allocating resources toward transportation networks, energy grids, and communication infrastructure to facilitate trade and improve connectivity both regionally and internationally [3]. By mitigating logistical barriers, Central Asian nations can enhance their appeal to foreign investors, especially those in export-oriented sectors.

Enhancing Financial Markets: The development of robust financial markets is crucial for attracting foreign direct investment (FDI), as they provide the necessary credit and capital for both foreign and domestic investors. Central Asian nations should focus on improving their financial institutions by enhancing credit accessibility,

developing capital markets, and ensuring macroeconomic stability. A resilient financial market is likely to boost investor confidence and contribute to the long-term sustainability of foreign direct investment inflows [1].

CONCLUSION

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) has the potential to significantly boost economic growth and promote sustainable development in Central Asian nations. However, the extent to which these benefits are realized depends on the policies and reforms implemented by the host countries. By enhancing governance, promoting sectoral diversification, providing competitive tax incentives, and encouraging Green Foreign Direct Investment, the governments of Central Asia can create a more attractive investment climate. This will ensure that FDI plays a crucial role in fostering long-term sustainable growth. Additionally, addressing challenges such as inadequate infrastructure and political instability is vital to unlocking the full potential of foreign direct investment in the region.

References

1. Abebaw, A. (2021). Corporate taxation and FDI within the EU. *European Financial Review*.
2. Bernhofer, F. (2014). The effect of FDI on infrastructure development. *Studies in Economics and Finance*, 2(4), 45-61.
3. Dreger, C., & Zhang, Y. (2011). The Chinese impact on GDP growth and inflation in the industrial countries. *Discussion Papers*, Deutsches Institut für Wirtschaftsforschung.
4. Doytch, N. (2015). FDI and economic growth: A sectoral approach. *World Development*, 67, 158-169.
5. Tuan, C. (2003). FDI and infrastructure development in Southeast Asia. *Journal of International Economics*, 42(3), 221-236.
6. Ugwu, J. I., & Okoye, E. I. (2018). Accounting for the effect of foreign direct investment on economic growth, post-IFRS adoption in selected Sub-Saharan African countries. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 8(2), 73-94.
7. Villaverde, J. (2015). FDI and sustainable development: The role of green investments. *Global Environmental Politics*, 15(2), 60-82.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Jtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokr ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2024. № 11

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.

Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77)

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77) telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

